

An Appraisal of the Impact of Ethical Issues and Religious Beliefs on the Nigerian Political Space

Pius Gudu

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi.

Emmanuel Emberga Amase

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi.

Abstract

Nigeria is recognized globally as a multi-ethnic and multi-religious nation, where religion plays important role in determining the political behaviour and attitudes of its citizens positively. Nevertheless, the interplay of religion and politics in Nigeria has also been a source of conflict, violence, and instability, especially since the return of democracy in the year 1999. This paper appraises the impact of ethical issues and religious beliefs on the Nigerian political space. The historical factor that influences the relationship between ethics, religion and politics in Nigeria is highlighted. The paper adopts a qualitative research design where data were sourced from secondary sources. The paper employed a historical method to highlight the relationship between politics, ethics and religion. The expository method was adopted to bring out the impact of ethical issues and religious beliefs on Nigerian political space while the analytical method was used to appraise the ethical issues, religious beliefs, politics and the challenges of national development in Nigeria. The findings of this paper are that religion and ethics have positively influenced the life of many nations including Nigeria and aided social progress and interpersonal cooperation and understanding among people. However, religion has been abused and politicized by bringing to play religious sentiments against one another. Thus the Nigerian political space is characterized by unethical practices which have led to gross underdevelopment. This work recommended among others that there should be balance and representation of different religious interests and perspectives in the Nigerian political system. To actualize this, there is a need for constitutional and institutional reforms that guarantee the rights and freedoms of all religious groups and actors. Such reforms can also prevent the abuse or manipulation of religion for political ends, as well as protect the secular nature of the state. The paper concludes that it is essential to understand and appreciate the roles and effects of religion and ethics in order to improve the development of the Nigeria political space.

Keywords: Politics, Ethics and Religion.

Introduction

Nigeria is a country with a rich and diverse cultural heritage, comprising over 250 ethnic groups and various religious affiliations. The Nigerian political space is characterized by a complex interplay of ethnic, religious, and regional factors, which often shape the political behaviour and orientation of the citizens and the political actors. However, the influence of ethics and religion on Nigerian politics has not always been positive or constructive. Rather, it has often been a source of conflict, violence, corruption, and underdevelopment. This paper appraises the impact of ethical issues and religious beliefs on the Nigerian political space, by examining the historical, theoretical, and empirical dimensions of this phenomenon. The paper identifies the challenges and opportunities that ethical issues and religious beliefs pose for the Nigerian politics, and provide some recommendations for enhancing the role of ethics and religion in promoting national development and integration.

Relationship between Politics, Ethics and Religion

Politics

From the Greek root (Polis -city-state), politics simply refers to the art of governance, a dynamic process that involves mobilizing human and other resources, managing, directing and implementation of public policies and regulatory decisions of a social order. In a broader sense, politics applies to various forms of organization and direction of human interests at different levels in society, including family, village, national, international and Church, according to a specific purpose. And within this general frame work, the world has witnessed many diverse political forms and types of government.¹ Politics includes the theory and practice that guides collective decision making for a group of people; it is the system of social unity, especially in the areas of public service, welfare, social amenities and the exercise of power to organize and control a particular community or state. Politics, in the traditional Greek sense, was used to refer to the search for the good in the governance of the polis; specifically the city or society. The aspects of traditional morality and political responsibility that Greek civilization left behind were aimed at providing a comfortable society for the members of the community. This is what Agulanna calls the ethical and responsible dimension of politics when he states: what a political society should do and how it should be constituted to achieve goalsthat arevaluabletothesociety.²

Ethics

The concept Ethics is not of English origins but Greek. Dzurgba in Aduke Adebayo is of the opinion that Ethics as an academic discipline was founded by Aristotle; a Greek philosopher. Aristotle created the noun *ethic* and its adjective *ethicos* in the Greek language. His contemporary Roman philosopher; Cicero coined the Latin equivalent of *moralitas* as the noun form and *moralis* as its adjectives.³ The English word, ethics, ethical etc, means custom, habit or conduct.⁴ Therefore, it is that ethics had its beginning in custom and usages, ‘Ethos and Mores’ of the people.⁵ Ethics is concerned with moral obligation, act, attitude or behaviour that is in line with practices commonly applauded within a given society, organization or environment. Ethics therefore includes honesty, tolerance compassion, service to other, courage and humane disposition to our fellow Nigerians.⁶ As to what constitutes national ethics in Nigeria, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 section 23 states: “national ethics shall be discipline, integrity, dignity of labour, social justice, religious tolerance, self-reliance and patriotism.”⁷

An action could, therefore, be referred to as good/right or bad/wrong if it tallies with or is against the nature of man. This is the foundation of the inalienable rights of all humanity, also referred as Universal Human Rights. To this extent, Ethics therefore forms the basis of politics as its issues (e.g. equality before the law, human dignity and basic rights of the individual) are predominantly ethical or moral in character. Furthermore, ethics relates to politics in terms of management of resources and regulation of social relationships in such manner that primary values of society such as justice, peace, individual and communal well-being are achieved and maintained.⁸ It is extremely important that the actions of each individual in society be consistent with the ethical standards that guide the community. This is because man is a social creature, unable to live a solitary life; therefore, its actions have an impact on the members of society. It implies that if he does well (good), the society will be peaceful and everyone will live in harmony, but if he does evil, evil will also have a negative impact on society. A society without moral consciousness is not worth living in and cannot be called society, because the activities of individuals in that society can only be compared with the activities of the state of nature as described by Thomas Hobbes.⁹

Religion

Harold Koenig says that “religion includes beliefs, practices, and rituals related to the divine, God, the mystical, or the supernatural. Religion is “an organized system of beliefs, rituals, practices, and worship centered on a supreme deity or deities”.¹⁰ Most of these religions share common characteristics, including: doctrines of faith and salvation, a range of acceptable behaviour, the use of sacred stories to support an opinion, religious rites

or conduct and ceremonies. Nigeria's three major religions (indigenous religions, Islam and Christianity) are ethical in nature. Each of them has a defined vision of the universe and reality in general as well as humanity's place in the (cosmological) order of things.¹¹

The power that humans wield ultimately originates from God and depends on God's sovereign providence. It is an essential aspect of God's plan for human personal and communal good. Omeregbe, opined that there are three ways in which religion can influence politics, namely, by the direct involvement of religious men in politics, by fusing the two (religion and politics) as one and by subjecting politics or government to the doctrine or laws of religion, thereby carrying out politics or governance along the line of religious doctrine, ideals or laws inseparable.¹²

Religion relates to politics in Africa in ways that are themselves linked to the particular historical and developmental trajectories of individual societies, whether traditional or modern. In pre-colonial African societies, the relationship between religion and politics was always a close one; it was not unusual that the chief priest determines the next ruler / king of a village, region, settlement et cetera. The religious beliefs and practices strengthened political power, while political concerns filter through the heart of the religious sphere. Rulers were not only political heads but also religious leaders whose well-being was closely linked to their people's health and welfare. However, the modernization process that accompanied European colonialism led to the secularization of public life and the de facto separation of politics and religion at the state level.¹³

Impact of Ethical Issues and Religious Beliefs on Nigerian Political Space

The impact of ethical and religious issues on Nigerian politics has both positive and negative effects. The impacts can be considered as follows:

Positive Impacts

Ethics is a body of principles or standards of human conduct that govern the behaviour of individuals and groups, which relates to the question of right or wrong and good or evil. When used in relation with leadership, ethics is concerned with the character of leaders and what they do in terms of their actions and behaviour because, it is a system of moral principles that governs or influences human behaviour. Today, the constitutions, laws and other documents of various countries contain codified ethical principles that guarantee the protection of their cherished values such as human rights, justice, public interest, impartiality, neutrality, equality and the common good. Other codes of conduct that are crafted to promote these values very often include financial regulation (FR), public service rules, due process, and due diligence, or transparency initiative.¹⁴

The positive impact of ethics on politics can be noticed in the adoption and practice of ethics of governance. The ethics of governance is about the incorporation of moral conditions and requirements in the management, governance, and control structures of organizations. However, the failure of governance of ethics in many countries threatens political, administrative, and developmental progress. Scholars have observed that there exists a strong relationship between corruption, the absence of ethics of governance, and maladministration. Ethics of good governance in public organisations emphasizes the need to have mechanisms in place that prevent or deal with potential conflicts of interest.¹⁵ On the other hand, the positive impact of religion on politics is that religion helps improve national development. As a matter of fact, history has shown that religion does foster national growth and development. In Nigeria, religion has greatly assisted in eradicating mass illiteracy. Indeed, the outstanding contributions of Christianity and Islam in the enlightenment and education of Nigerians cannot be overemphasized. Both religions have played significant roles in the evolution of a literate culture in Nigeria. This was through the establishments of the various missionary and Quranic schools in Nigeria.¹⁶

It is pertinent to note that virtually every religion does not tolerate immorality. Thus, adhering to religious moral values is mandatory for all religious practitioners. In this sense, religious moral values are expected to manifest at every point of influence. This means that religious people are obligated to uphold the moral teachings inherent in their religion and provide good leadership and obedient followers. Religion provides mankind with

moral values by which to live.¹⁷ Every religion whether Christianity, Islam, African Traditional Religion, etc., has moral values which regulate and harmonize human life. For instance, In Exodus 20 of the Christian Bible, there is an outline of the Ten Commandments which guide the behaviour of Christians in the society. Likewise, Islam and African Traditional Religions (ATR) have rules that their followers must follow.

Religion, as an agent of social control, helps maintain social norms, which are the true foundation of politics. Therefore, smooth elections will produce legitimate leaders who will rule in the fear of God; and obedient disciples. Achieving this will solve problems such as political instability, violence and insecurity, mismanagement, embezzlement, corruption, nepotism, religious intolerance and god fatherism, which are clearly the product of abuse of moral principles. Johnstone corroborates this view that what people believe, regarding what is good, true and desirable as well as what God wants for people and society can influence the choices they make in the political arena. In other words, religion will affect people's voting habits.¹⁸ Finally, it should be noted that Nigerian politicians were also convinced of the positive impact of ethics on national development and thus have championed that amoral revolution would change Nigeria's political destiny. This can be inferred from President Shehu Shagari's launch of the Ethical Revolution in 1982, followed by the military junta's War Against Indiscipline (WAI), all of which openly admitted Nigeria's inability to maintain the basic, universally accepted ethical standards that underpin good political behaviour and ensure the success of prescribed common goals.¹⁹ In reality, the positive effects are hypothetical as religious ethical values have no impact on governance in Nigeria since independence. While no leader, past or present claims to be non-religious, what is being experienced is religious manipulation, the effects of which on national development will be analyzed below.

Negative Impacts

The common slogan of some people in Nigeria that, "politics is a dirty game" needs moral evaluation. This simple slogan has a lot of social, religious and moral implications in the country. Both the literal and figurative meanings of the statement are that by nature, politics is dirty in itself. This implies that politics has nothing to do with morality, since it is asserted to be a dirty endeavour. The Nigerian political space has been operating on this wrong political notion and ideology. The obvious effect of this is seen in the pervasive corruption, Machiavellianism, embezzlement, rigging, and killing that have taken over the Nigerian political space.²⁰

The negative impact of religion on politics is characterized by "politicization of religion and religionization of politics."²¹ Politicization can be said to be a procedure whereby the norm is overthrown and an ulterior agenda prioritized. Politicization of religion which is one of the precursors of political polarization is increasingly taken over the Nigerian political space. Hence religious acrimony is evident in different parts of Nigeria. In recent times, religion has taken a central space in politics and public life. Its politicization has become the norm such that religion has become a "magical wand" that politicians wave at as they deem fit to sway the electorate in their favour.²²

Religious issues have influenced the electoral process in Nigeria in many ways. One of such is religious-distrust. Each religious denomination is distrustful of the other hence is unwilling to trust power into the hands of political leaders who are from other religious denomination. Thus, religion often determines the choice of flag bearers and their running mate for the posts of the president and governor in some states. This is done to ensure that the interests of adherents are protected. Where this principle is adopted, there is usually a Muslim/Christian or Christian/Muslim ticket. Thus in 1979, the National Party of Nigeria (NPN) adopted a Muslim/Christian ticket while the Unity Party of Nigeria (U.P.N) did not take religion into consideration, hence its adoption of a Christian/Christian ticket²³. Perhaps, Chief Awolowo saw this as one of the reasons why he lost and chose a Muslim from the North as his running mate in 1983. Even some military regimes recognized religion as a factor in governance. For instance, the Murtala/Obasanjo era was a Muslim/Christian ticket and Obasanjo, upon becoming the Head of State, chose a Muslim as his deputy. Both Abacha and Abubakar maintained the status quo as they picked Diya and Akhigbe (Christians) as their second in command, respectively. During civilian regime, the Obasanjo/Atiku regime was Christian/Muslim, Yar'dua/Jonathan was Muslim/Christian; Jonathan/Sambo

was Christian/Muslim, Buhari/Osibanjo was Muslim/Christian and the current regime of Tinubu/Shettima which is Muslim/ Muslim almost divided the country as Christians kicked against their candidature.²⁴

Boko Haram's theology and politics goes beyond hatred for Western influence. Its worldview is expressed in two broader ideas. First, it is a religious exclusivism that opposes all other value systems, including rival interpretations of Islam. This exclusivism insists and demands that Muslims must choose between their brand of Islam and a set of allegedly anti-Islamic practices such as: democracy, constitutionalism, alliances with non-Muslims, and Western-style education. Therefore, theirs is a politics of victimhood. Boko Haram claims that its violence is a response to what it views as a decades-long history of persecution against Muslims in Nigeria.²⁵ Voting and campaigns are based on religious sentiment. In this case, religion could be used to either canvass support for a candidate or dissuade the electorate from voting for him or her. Merit is usually sacrificed for religious partisanship during voting. Religion is used as an effective instrument during national elections to create specific vote blocks, especially prior to elections. The problems, by and large, persist in the assumption that parties or movements are only successful if they invoke religious identity during elections. The strategies used by certain religious groups are to devise and carve roles for themselves in politics by bringing to play religious sentiments against one another. The modus operandi is to present themselves as true champions of their religion and whip up emotions in their favour.²⁶

Nigerian politicians have separated moral issues from politics; they lead us to believe that politics and morality cannot be reconciled. The idea is that once a person starts politics, they have to abandon morality, hence the saying "politics is a dirty game". They believe that it is important to hold political power by all means, whether good or bad, and maintain it in the same way. The goal of any government is to meet the needs of the people, but this is not the goal of these corrupt Nigerian leaders, because the means of gaining political power justify their selfish goals.²⁷ Dzurgba identifies the causes of the collapse of the first Nigerian Republic to include: abuse of economic resources, corruption, nepotism, lawlessness, recklessness, discipline, dishonesty, waste, abuse of political power, denial of human rights and reciprocal relationships, jealousy, brutality, oppression, repression, election fraud, inflated census figures and bloody violence or riots and consequently concludes that "all these causes are more ethical than anything else we can think of."²⁸

The electoral processes in Nigeria have not been free and fair since the inception of democracy in the country. Nigeria is a country where the elected politician would confess through media that the election that brought him to the position was full of abnormalities without resigning from that office and nothing will follow his confession. Familusi asserts that elections in Nigeria since her independence has been fraught with all manner of irregularities ranging from malpractices to violence. He identifies immorality, political illiteracy and monetization of politics as the factors responsible for the deplorable state of elections in the country.²⁹ Electoral malpractice is inimical to the democratic development of any nation and it is a sign of lack of respect for the will of the electorates to choose who is to lead them. It is not a new thing to record ballot box snatching, killing, militarization of election, inflation of number of the cast votes and many other immoral activities in Nigeria elections, and this has been identified as one of the cogs in wheel of progress of the nation. We cannot but condemn the unethical act of purchasing votes that is common in Nigerian politics. It is pertinent to note that Religion is mostly expected to translate to high moral standards, impeccable ethics, beliefs and values; anything contrary to the aforementioned is seen as an aberration. It is therefore disheartening to observe that rather than religion influencing the polity to higher levels of values, attitudes and beliefs, there appears to be a degeneration of these attributes.³⁰

Ethics, Religion, Politics and the Challenges of National Development in Nigeria

With more than four hundred ethnic groups, Nigeria is a multi-ethnic nation state and these groups practice differing religion. Nigeria has been grappling and trying to cope with the problem of development since independence. This is because over the years the phenomena of religious intolerance and unethical political practices have led to incessant recurrence of ethno-religious conflicts. A major cause of conflicts in Nigeria

revolves around religious issues such as religious intolerance, overzealousness, bigotry, suspicion, distrust and manipulation. Whereas ethical issues such as accusations and allegations of neglect, oppression, domination, exploitation, victimization, discrimination, marginalization, nepotism, corruption, dishonesty and lack of accountability have suffocated the Nigerian political space.

Thus, in Nigeria, there appears to be frosty relations between politics, ethics and religion thereby leading to the rise of militancy among various ethnic and religious groups. These crises have given birth to many militant groups like the Boko Haram, Maitatsine, Independent Peoples of Biafra (IPOB), O'dua Peoples' Congress (OPC); the Bakassi Boys; the Egbesu Boys; the various Niger Delta Agitators, the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB).³¹ The emergence of these ethnic and religious militias has created deep divides between the various ethnic and religious groups, hence intolerance has become more violent and bloody with more devastating results. These militias are used as the executors of ethno-religious agenda.

Another major challenge experienced in the Nigeria political space is the breakdown of such vehicles of social control that characterized the traditional African societies such as the family, education, law, religion and political system that cared for the well-being of all citizens. Indeed, the malfunctioning of all these important institutions has actually increased ethnic and communal conflicts in Nigeria. For instance, the inability of many homes to make the ends meet with the family income tends to increase immorality, broken fatherless/motherless homes, divorces and drunkenness, leading again to a large reserve of youths who could be employed for execution of ethno-religious conflicts.³²

Recommendations

Religious tolerance and harmony among Nigerians should be promoted. To achieve that, there is a need for interfaith dialogue and cooperation among different religious groups and leaders. Such dialogue can foster mutual understanding, respect, and trust, as well as address common issues and challenges that affect the nation. Integrity of Nigerian politics should be enhanced. To accomplish this, there is a need for ethical education and awareness among both political actors and citizens. Such education can instill moral values and principles, such as honesty, accountability, transparency, and fairness, as well as foster civic responsibility and participation. There should be balance and representation of different religious interests and perspectives in the Nigerian political system. To actualize this, there is a need for constitutional and institutional reforms that guarantee the rights and freedoms of all religious groups and actors. Such reforms can also prevent the abuse or manipulation of religion for political ends, as well as protect the secular nature of the state.

Conclusion

The impact of ethical issues and religious beliefs on the Nigerian political space or politics is a complex and controversial one that has both positive and negative implications. Religion can serve as a source of identity, mobilization, values, norms, power, and influence for Nigerians, but it can also create divisions, conflicts, dilemmas, contradictions, contention, and competition among them. Religion and ethics are important factors that shape the Nigerian political space or politics. They have significant impacts on the behaviour, attitudes, and outcomes of both political actors and citizens. Therefore, it is essential to understand and appreciate their roles and effects in order to improve the development of the Nigeria political space.

Endnotes

¹Chris. I. Ejizu, "Ethics of Politics in Nigeria: The Christian Perspective," *Bulletin of Ecumenical Theology* 2.1(1989): 46-58.

²C.O. Agulanna, "Moral & Political Education as Foundation for a Reasonable Social Order in Africa," in F.A. Adeigbo et al, *Ethics and Public Affairs* (Ibadan: Ibadan University Press, 2014), 27.

³Akpenpuun Dzurgba, "General Issues in Professional Ethics," in Adebayo Aduke (ed.), *Contemporary Issues in Professional Ethics* (Ibadan: Graduke Publishers, 2011), 1-13.

⁴Shields Norman. *Christian Ethics* (Nigeria: Africa Christian Textbooks, 2004), 1.

⁵Balkrishna S. Pandit, *Ethics* (Delhi: Surjeet Book Depot (s) Regd, ND), 1.

- ⁶Akpanim N. Ekpe and Martha A. Ekpe, "Ethics and Democratic Governance in Nigeria," *INTUITION* 5.1 (2013) : 286-295.
- ⁷Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999.
- ⁸Chris I. Ejizu, "Ethics of Politics in Nigeria: The Christian Perspective,"...47-58.
- ⁹Joseph I. Omeregbe, *Ethics: A Systematic and Historical Study* (Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers Limited 1993), 148.
- ¹⁰Harold G. Koenig, "Research on Religion, Spirituality, and Mental Health: A Review," *Canadian journal of psychiatry. Revue canadienne de psychiatrie* 54.5 (2009): 283-291.
- ¹¹Ogunbado Ahamad, "Impacts of Colonialism on Religions: An Experience of Southwestern Nigeria," *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 5.4 (2012): 51-57.
- ¹²Joseph I. Omeregbe, "Recognising Ethics as a Path to National Greatness," in Maduabuchi Dukor (ed). *Philosophy and Politics: Discourse in Values, Politics and Power in Africa* (Lagos: Malthouse Press Ltd, 2003), 386-393.
- ¹³Olufunmilayo Oyelude and Jones O. Aluko, "Politicization of Religion and the Ethical Implications in Africa," *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews* 12.1 (2022): 364 – 373.
- ¹⁴Walshak Alheri Danfulani and Umar Habila Dadem Danfulani, "Ethics, Politics and Good Governance in Nigeria: The Problem of Entrenching Values in the Face of Increasing Corruption," *African Journal of Philosophy and Studies* 1.1 (July 2019): 1-21.
- ¹⁵Igwe P. A., Egbo O. P., Nwakpu S. E., Hove-Sibanda P., Mohammad Saif A. N. and Islam M. A., "Content Analysis of Ethics of Governance, Maladministration and Political Corruption," *International Journal of Public Sociology and Socioterapy* 1. 2 (2021):15-32.
- ¹⁶Rimamsikwe Habila Kitause and Hilary Chukwuka Achunike, "Religion in Nigeria from 1900-2013," *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences* 3.18, (2013): 45-57.
- ¹⁷Daniel Sunday Ajayi, "Towards the Enhancement of Morality in the Nigerian Politics,"...1-20.
- ¹⁸Johnstone R.L., *Religion in Society: A Sociology of Religion*. (New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 2001), 103.
- ¹⁹Chris I. Ejizu, "Ethics of Politics in Nigeria: The Christian Perspective,"...47-58.
- ²⁰Daniel Sunday Ajayi, "Towards the Enhancement of Morality in the Nigerian Politics,"...1-20.
- ²¹Adogame A., "Politicization of Religion and Religionization of Politics in Nigeria," in C.J. Korieh and G.U. Nwokeji (eds.), *Religion, History, and Politics in Nigeria* (Oxford: University Press of America 2006), 128.
- ²²Olufunmilayo, Oyelude and Jones O. Aluko, "Politicization of Religion and the Ethical Implications in Africa," *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews* 12.1 (2022): 364 – 373.
- ²³Ayantayo J.K., "Religious Factors in the Nigerian Public Sphere: Burdens and Prospects," *Africa Development* 34. 3.4, (2009): 93-109.
- ²⁴Ikenna L. Umeanolue, "Religious Influences on Politics in Nigeria: Implications for National Development," *OGIRISI: A New Journal of African Studies* 15 (2020): 139-157.
- ²⁵Alex Thurston, "The Disease is Unbelief": Boko Haram's Religious and Political Worldview," The Brookings Project on U.S. Relations with the Islamic World, *ANALYSIS PAPER*, No. 22, (2016):1-30.
- ²⁶Adamo D., "Religion and elections in Nigeria: A Historical Perspective", *Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae* 44.3 (2018): 1-19.
- ²⁷Daniel Sunday Ajayi, "Towards the Enhancement of Morality in the Nigerian Politics"... 1-20.
- ²⁸Akpenpuun Dzurgba, "The Relevance of Christian Ethics in the Search for Political Values in Nigeria," (Unpubl. Ph.D. Thesis, Nsukka, 1984): 196.
- ²⁹Familusi O.O., "A Religious Ethical Evaluation of Electoral Malpractices in Nigeria," *Orita: Ibadan Journal of Religious Studies* 42.1 (2012): 89-112.
- ³⁰Adenugba A.A. and Omolewa S.A., "Religious Values and Corruption in Nigeria: A Dislocated Relationship," *Journal of Education and Social Research* 4.3 (2014): 522- 528.
- ³¹Salawu B., "Ethno-Religious Conflicts in Nigeria: Causal Analysis and Proposals for New Management Strategies," *European Journal of Social Sciences* 13.3 (2010): 345-353.
- ³²Salawu B., "Ethno-Religious Conflicts in Nigeria: Causal Analysis and Proposals for New Management Strategies,"... 345-353.